

Exam Protocol

Patient Info:

Name: [REDACTED]

Sex: F ID: P44677

Patient Position: HFS

07-Nov-19 13:02:28

1	3D	FIXED	6sDCT Body	6s	60F/s	07-Nov-19 13:43:32
A	99kV 498mA	4.1ms	0.1CL large 0.0Cu 48cm	5511.7 μ Gym ²	179mGy	169RAO 0CRA 397F
2	3D	FIXED	6sDCT Body	6s	60F/s	07-Nov-19 13:59:54
A	93kV 296mA	3.7ms	0.2CL large 0.0Cu 48cm	3055.8 μ Gym ²	99mGy	169RAO 0CRA 397F
3	3D	FIXED	6sDCT Body	6s	60F/s	07-Nov-19 14:09:47
A	92kV 358mA	3.7ms	0.2CL large 0.0Cu 48cm	3241.5 μ Gym ²	105mGy	169RAO 0CRA 397F
4	3D	FIXED	6sDCT Body	6s	60F/s	07-Nov-19 14:19:31
A	94kV 323mA	3.7ms	0.3CL large 0.0Cu 48cm	3186.9 μ Gym ²	103mGy	169RAO 0CRA 397F

Accumulated exposure data

07-Nov-19 14:48:24

Performing Physician: Fiore

Exposures: 4

Total Fluoro: 00:01:29

Total: 16706 μ Gym² 541.6mGy

A Fluoro: 00:01:29 1710.1 μ Gym² 55.5mGy

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